

How to promote multifunctionality of vegetated strips in arable farming: A qualitative approach for Germany

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Abstract

Vegetated strips are in the focus of many stakeholders of agroecosystems and are part of several agri-environmental schemes in Germany. Stakeholders have different expectations and demands on the functionality and services of vegetated strips. In our review, we focused on biodiversity and the ecosystem services pollination, conservation biocontrol, landscape aesthetics, buffer function, and biomass production and their associated functions. We assessed factors that are crucial to support service provision and reviewed trade-offs between the ecosystem (dis)services. We identified five characteristics that are important for the provision of the assessed ecosystem services: age of vegetated strips, flower cover, size or width of the strip, management, and type of adjacent habitat. We conclude that adjusting the target of subsidies with respect to the analyzed factors for biodiversity can help to promote the multifunctionality of vegetated strips in arable farming.

KEYWORDS

agroecosystem, arable farming, buffer, conservation biocontrol, disservices, ecosystem services, field margin, filter, flower strip, multifunctionality, traits

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable food production depends on agroecosystem–biodiversity and related ecosystem services (Dainese et al., 2019; World Resources Institute, 2005). However, a decline in biodiversity in farmlands has been observed for several groups of organisms including birds (Busch et al., 2020; Gregory et al., 2004) and insects (Seibold et al., 2019; Vogel, 2017) over several decades (Tschardt et al., 2005). The major driving force of farmland biodiversity loss is agricultural intensification with increased farm and field sizes, specialization, and management intensity (Benton et al., 2003; Emmerson et al., 2016; Geiger et al., 2010; Tschardt et al., 2021) and

at the same time, a decrease of seminatural habitats (Billetter et al., 2008; Geiger et al., 2010; Leuschner et al., 2014; Meyer et al., 2014; Tschardt et al., 2005).

Highly diverse ecosystems are considered to be more stable and thus make ecosystem services more reliable through the redundancy of functional species, functional facilitation, and niche complementarity (Cadotte et al., 2011; Hector et al., 2010).

Vegetated strips such as field margins are part of any agroecosystem and provide a large part of seminatural habitats in the agroecosystem (Marshall & Moonen, 2002; Mkenda et al., 2019). In particular, flowering strips are usually sown at the edge of the field but also as a strip inside the crop (Albrecht et al., 2020). Many expectations are

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associated with the functions and ecosystem services that these vegetated strips provide (Balzan & Moonen, 2014; Campbell et al., 2017; Grigg et al., 2018; Haaland et al., 2011; Hackett & Lawrence, 2014; Haddaway et al., 2018; Marshall & Moonen, 2002). They can supply various fundamental ecosystem services relevant for the agroecosystem and the farmer, such as provisioning services (e.g., biomass production) or supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling, habitat provision, and/or connectivity and maintenance of genetic diversity) as well as regulating services such as buffer functions (i.e., erosion control, filter function, distance), pollination, and conservation biocontrol with possible spillover effects into the adjacent agricultural field. In addition, cultural ecosystem services with value for the society (i.e., aesthetics, cultural heritage) are provided by vegetated strips.

Vegetated strips and in particular flower strips have been introduced as promising measures in agri-environmental schemes (AES). Depending on management preferences or the requirements of the AES, they are maintained for 1 year only or for up to 5 years. It can be assumed that temporary structures are attractive to farmers, because they can be relocated and thus adapted to the current crop rotation. Furthermore, vegetated strips require little space and can easily be integrated into farming practices. They can simplify field cultivation and save time and fuel, for example, when selecting edge locations of uneven, asymmetrical fields that are difficult to work (Fuchs & Stein-Bachinger, 2008).

National and European strategies refer to vegetated strips explicitly as tools for enriching and diversifying agricultural landscapes, yet with different purposes. The German National Action Plan on Sustainable Use of Plant Protection Products (BMEL, 2013) targets the raising of the proportion of habitats and retreat areas in the agricultural landscape. These landscapes should compromise up to 10% of seminatural habitats by 2023. This target is in line with the German Arable Farming Strategy 2035 (BMEL, 2021) and with biodiversity strategies on national (BMUB, 2007) and European levels (COM, 2020).

In Germany, the area of vegetated strips reported as ecological focus areas in 2020 under the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU (CAP)-Greening amounted to about 23,200 ha (BMEL, 2020a). The number of flower strips is probably higher, because they are not always reported in this category, for example, since other options are easier to fulfill the Greening requirements. Additionally, Federal States fund AES including flowering strips. In 2018, flowering strips were sown on more than 117,000 ha (DBV, 2019), which accounts for 1% of the total area of arable land (11,731,000 ha) (Destatis, 2019) in Germany. Vegetated strips also serve as buffer strips that are created to prevent wind and water erosion along contour lines or water bodies. They are expected to have a filter

function to protect habitats, water bodies, and nontarget organisms behind the buffer strip from pesticide drift or leaching of fertilizers. Thus, buffer strips are currently mandatory under the Common Agricultural Policy (European Commission, 2022). According to the German Federal Water Act and state laws on water, vegetated buffer strips with a minimum width of 5 m must be established along a ditch or watercourse (Umweltbundesamt, 2018). The estimated area of riparian buffer strips in Germany amounts to 127,000 ha (Balzer & Schulz, 2012). Similar legislation exists for other European countries to comply with the Water Framework Directive, the Nitrates Directive, or in Cross Compliance with the good agricultural and environmental conditions and the Sustainable Use Directive (Balana et al., 2012; Barnett, 2009; Stutter et al., 2012).

Vegetated strips have been studied and reviewed by various research groups. While the majority of publications focus on only one ecosystem service, fewer studies address multifunctionality, for example, by demonstrating the impact of the landscape configuration on different ecosystem services provided by vegetated strips (Tscharntke et al., 2005) and disservices (Marshall & Moonen, 2002). A systematic map of the literature published until 2015 on vegetated strips in the northern temperate boreal zone presents 64 studies for Germany (Haddaway et al., 2018). However, only three reviews addressing and analyzing ecosystem services were identified for Central and Northern Europe (Haaland et al., 2011; Marshall, 2005; Wilson et al., 1999).

In order to account for the latest developments, we conducted an up-to-date literature review, also with regard to current funding policies. Here, we focus on vegetated strips on arable land in Central and Northern Europe with a specific emphasis on Germany. Our aim is to investigate vegetated strips and their contribution to the provision of multifunctional ecosystem services. We reviewed the literature on the different requirements and expectations for vegetated strip functions and services to answer the following questions:

1. What are the single and/or multiple ecosystem services provided by vegetated strips?
2. Which characteristics of vegetated strips are relevant for the provision of specific and multifunctional services?
3. How can vegetated strips be designed and managed in order to deliver multiple ecosystem services?

Moreover, in the *Discussion*, we will address questions on the benefits and effects vegetated strips achieve for biodiversity, their general acceptance, and whether the policy frameworks and related measures support biodiversity enhancement and pollution reduction related to vegetated strips.

METHODOLOGY

Due to the complexity of factors and traits important for different ecosystem services, we chose an integrative and semi-systematic approach with a qualitative analysis for the literature review (Snyder, 2019).

Terms for vegetated strips vary according to differences in their purpose, method of establishment and maintenance, and ownership. We consider all types of planted or naturally vegetated field margin strips, such as wildflower strips, flowering margins, grass strips, riparian strips, or buffer strips. For generalization, we refer to them as vegetated strips or simply field margins. We distinguish vegetated strips from crop edge and hedges (Hackett & Lawrence, 2014; Marshall & Moonen, 2002), which are not included in our review.

For our review, we define “trait” as a characteristic or management-related property of the vegetated strip that influences ecosystem service provision. Our aim was to identify traits that influence service provision. We started the literature search with the results of the extensive literature search by Haddaway et al. (2018) that was completed in late 2015. We then conducted an additional search to add more recent publications. We used “Web of Science,” including the Web of Science Core Collection database (1945 until May 2020) and “Google Scholar” and the “OpenAgrar” data repository, with no restriction in years. Between December 2018 and March 2020, we searched with the following keywords in English and German language. For a publication to be included, it had to contain (1) “*field margin*,” “*flower* strip*,” “*grass margin*,” “*vegetated strip*” or in German “*Feldrand*,” “*Feldsaum*,” “*Feldrain*,” “*Ackerschonstreifen*,” “*Blühstreifen*,” “*Ackerrandstreifen*”; (2) information about an ecosystem service “*biocontrol*,” “*sedimentation*,” “*buffer*,” “*erosion*,” “*Nitrogen*,” “*Phosphorus*,” “*pesticides*,” “*pollination*,” “*biodiversity conservation*,” “*habitat management*,” “*biomass*,” “*biogas*” and “*aesthetics*” or in German “*biologische Kontrolle*,” “*Nutzinsekten*,” “*Nützlinge*,” “*Filter*,” “*Puffer*,” “*Erosion*,” “*Stickstoff*,” “*Phosphor*,” “*Pflanzenschutzmittel*,” “*Bestäub**,” “*Biodiversität*,” “*Habitatmanagement*” “*Biomasse*,” “*Biogas*,” and “*Landschaftsbild*.” We included peer-reviewed literature, original research papers as well as review papers, and gray literature, since some relevant studies for Germany were published only as reports.

We restricted our review to arable cropping systems and excluded publications on perennial systems like grassland, orchards, and vineyards. We excluded papers without focus on Central and Northern Europe.

Studies without statistically significant results or without identifying a trait as having an impact on service provision of the selected ecosystem services were excluded.

Initially we screened 433 publications. After the selection process, 104 publications were included in our review (biodiversity conservation: 49; pollination: 13; conservation biocontrol: 40; buffer function: 9; disservices: 9). Traits were extracted from the publications when a comparison was made between two traits. Multitrait relationships are discussed in the text, but were not included in Tables S1–S5 in the Appendix S1.

We grouped the identified traits into four groups concerning (1) certain species (15 traits), (2) the management of the strip (11 traits), (3) the habitat structure (6 traits), and (4) the position or configuration of the strip (4 traits).

Additionally, the following information was extracted from the studies: the target species for biodiversity conservation, pollination, and conservation biocontrol; the pest species, crop, and distance effect that was measured for biocontrol; the contaminant and transport medium for buffer function; the pest or weed species and affected crop for disservices. Results were split by measured effects at species level and ecosystem service level for pollination and conservation biocontrol. Width and age of the vegetated strip were recorded if it was tested for.

RESULTS

Our review led to the identification of six important ecosystem services (summarized in Figure 1) provided by vegetated strips, which can be linked to the environment and society (in green) as well as the agricultural production (in yellow) in agroecosystems.

In the following, we structure our results according to our research questions: First, we present (1) a brief overview of the key ecosystem services (and disservices) of vegetated strips, followed by (2) the main characteristics associated with their provision, and (3) recommendations for their design and management. We address each question along the ecosystem services illustrated in Figure 1, starting with the top row services linked to environment and society, followed by services linked to agricultural production.

What are the single and/or multiple ecosystem services provided by vegetated strips?

Vegetated strips benefit associated farmland biodiversity and the agroecosystem as they can fulfill various functions for biodiversity, such as the provision of habitats, food, nesting sites, and hiding places, while also guaranteeing structural connectivity between habitats

FIGURE 1 Six central ecosystem services and their associated function provided by vegetated strips, selection based on importance and interaction with agricultural production. Yellow denotes services linked to the agricultural production system. Green denotes services linked to society and environment.

and maintaining genetic diversity of adapted autochthonous species (Marshall & Moonen, 2002). Moreover, vegetated strips deliver cultural ecosystem services to society, provide landscape aesthetics, advertise the image of farmers, and allow for recreation. Flower strips, in particular, are in focus and in favor of the public for their aesthetic aspects (Lindemann-Matthies & Bose, 2007).

The spatial and structural richness and characteristics of vegetated strips mediate other biodiversity-based ecosystem services provided by organisms, such as pollination (Kleijn et al., 2015) and conservation biocontrol (Gillespie et al., 2016; Heimpel & Jervis, 2005; Tschumi, Albrecht, Collatz, et al., 2016). Additionally, the temporal aspects of flower strips can affect pollination, especially honey bees and bumblebees (e.g., by extending resource availability for pollinators; Wagner, 2014) and conservation biocontrol (by providing winter/off-season refuge for populations of beneficial arthropods as a source of recolonization; Dennis et al., 1994; Pfiffner & Luka, 2000; Welling et al., 1994).

Beyond the ecosystem services provided by organisms, vegetated strips can fulfill a filter and buffer function, mitigating erosion and pollution from pesticides and nutrients as they tend to reduce flow velocities and therefore intercept runoff from agricultural fields (Helmerts et al., 2008).

For this purpose, in-field, edge-of-field, and off-field buffers are common, which are relatively easy to implement and verify for control purposes (Alix et al., 2017).

Biomass production from flower strips could increase the attractiveness of flower strips for farmers. The utilization of the annual cut vegetation is discussed as a compensation for reduction of field size and as an economic incentive, that is, biomass production of flower strips used for fodder or biogas (Degenbeck, 2020; von Redwitz et al., 2019). However, under current German legislation, the utilization of flower strip biomass is not allowed (Müller & Hahn, 2020).

We fully acknowledge that besides the positive effects, vegetated strips can also deliver ecosystem disservices that impact the adjacent crop: For example, wild plant communities may harbor weeds (De Cauwer et al., 2008), pests, and pathogens (Burdon, 1993; Gilbert, 2002; Keesing et al., 2006; McCabe et al., 2017; Mitchell & Power, 2006). Also, vegetated strips may provide shelter for mammalian pests such as rodents which that prefer crop seeds over weed seeds (Tschumi et al., 2018). However, in the following, we focus on the six central ecosystem services provided by vegetated strips summarized in Figure 1 and do not address those disservices in detail.

What characteristics of vegetated strips are responsible for the provision of specific and multifunctional services?

We have summarized the characteristics and attributes that promote the six identified benefits of vegetated strips in Table 1. More details including the references are given in Appendix S1: Tables S1–S5.

One of the most consistent traits with a positive impact on “biodiversity” and a broad range of target organisms (e.g., birds, mice, and diverse insect groups) is vegetation composition (i.e., diverse plant species composition with a high functional diversity), favoring high flower abundance and complex vegetation structure (predominantly via vegetation architecture and height). Also, the age of a vegetated strip (annual vs. perennial), strip management (number and timing of cuts), and its size and width favor biodiversity. Appendix S1: Table S1 gives an overview of the traits and their associated different target species or species groups.

Studies on “landscape aesthetics” were able to determine factors valued by the public, such as species richness and diversity (Junge et al., 2009). Especially brightly colored, large flowers (Lindemann-Matthies & Bose, 2007), the duration of flowering in the vegetated strip (Akbar et al., 2003; Clay & Daniel, 2000), and vegetation height of <1.5 m are preferred qualities of flower strips and meadows (Nohl, 2001). Besides these characteristics, the location of the flower strips had a strong influence on the landscape and its perception. For recreation, strips should be placed at the edges of roads where they can be easily perceived and directly experienced (Reich et al., 2015). Conversely, for many farmers, a clean and orderly landscape is important, showing their skills and engagement, which can be inconsistent with an unkempt field margin to promote biodiversity (Burton, 2004; Junge et al., 2009).

Many “pollinators” such as bees and bumblebees are very mobile, covering large areas, and therefore their pollination service is less restricted by distance but more strongly affected by the quality of surrounding habitats (Pywell et al., 2006; Woodcock et al., 2016). Especially a high flower cover in vegetated strips is attractive for pollinators, thus favoring pollination in general (Feltham et al., 2015; Korpela et al., 2013) and also has the potential to increase crop pollination of adjacent fields (Albrecht et al., 2020; Zamorano et al., 2020). However, there are species-specific differences in response within and between studies. While visitation rates of honeybees were not affected along a 200 m transect into the crop, visitation rate of solitary bees and bumblebees declined (Woodcock et al., 2016). In comparison, Pywell et al. (2006) observed that bumblebees foraged at distances of 1 km or more.

In Appendix S1: Table S2, we present an overview of traits that enhance pollinator abundance and diversity, as well as pollination, emphasizing the importance of resource quality traits over distance. The most prominent traits observed in our literature were flower abundance and associated pollen and nectar availability to favor bees and bumblebees (four studies), nesting site presence for solitary bees and bumblebees (three studies), UV patterns of flowers (two studies), and the effects of seed mixtures, age, and temporal variation in flower strips (two studies). Vegetated strips provide natural habitats for beneficial insects, but the performance of beneficials and the efficiency of their biocontrol strongly depend on the cultivated crops, pest occurrence, and environmental conditions (Boetzel et al., 2020; Tschardt et al., 2016).

For the enhancement of “conservation biocontrol,” the most studied traits in the literature were flower abundance, pollen and nectar availability, flower morphology, and thus attractiveness to natural enemies. Other traits are the provision of habitat and refuge, especially for overwintering to allow natural enemies to re-migrate into the field. The age of the vegetated strip is also considered. Higher age of vegetated strips has been shown to be favorable for parasitoids (Thies & Tschardt, 1999) and spiders (Denys & Tschardt, 2001). A greater pest control potential is assumed for very mobile species such as lady beetles and hoverflies, the common natural enemies of cereal aphids; with a range of up to 500 m and more (Boller et al., 2004) they move easily into the crop when prey is present. In contrast, the less mobile lacewings and spiders are of minor importance for biological control of cereal aphids (Freier et al., 1997). Conservation biocontrol may only be effective at a short distance, such as for the pollen beetle (Skellern & Cook, 2018). Only a few studies on biological pest control (Büchi, 2002; Pfister et al., 2017; Woodcock et al., 2016) have investigated distances of more than 25 m into the field (see Appendix S1: Table S3, where the traits that influence conservation biocontrol effects of vegetated strips are summarized).

Relevant characteristics of vegetated strips to improve “buffer functions” depend on the respective environmental conditions (soil and water flows), plant species composition, and the width of structures, as well as age and location. In their review on buffer strips, Dabney et al. (2006) found that even narrow buffers improve water quality. Nonetheless, the effectiveness increases with dimension (Reichenberger et al., 2007). Buffers work best on slow, shallow diffuse flows, where they slow down, trap, and enhance the metabolism of pesticides and on shallow soils, which are most susceptible to runoff. Additional in-field practices such as residue management, cover crops, contour plowing, and crop rotations can further enhance their effectiveness. From the

TABLE 1 Overview of traits that foster ecosystem (dis)service provision.

Trait by category	Biodiversity conservation	Pollination	Biocontrol	Filter/buffer function	Biomass provision	Aesthetics	Pests	Weeds
Species								
Plant diversity	3		1			1		
Presence of specific plant species	3	3			1	1	2	
Seeds of autochthonous populations and genotypes (flower strips)	1							
Densely tillered, deep rooted grass species				1				
High proportion of grasses				1				
Grass species with stiff stalks				1				
Resilience of the vegetation to drought and submergence				1				
Flower abundance	3	5	4			4		
Pollen and nectar availability	1	1	5					
Presence of floral resources in the late season		1				1		
Selection of (flowers with) pollen for specific beneficial insects			1					
Flower morphology			7			1		
Presence of complementary enemies			2					
Presence of alternate hosts for parasitoids			1					
Presence of earthworms and their burrows	4							
Management								
Avoidance of runoff of fertilizers from the field	2							
Avoidance of pesticide spray drift from the field	1							
Timing of cuts	7							1
Biomass removal	1			1				1
Breaking the dominance of grasses	1							
Early sowing of flower strips	1							
Wide variety of seed mixtures/ temporal variation in sowing time of flower strips		1						
Higher age of the strip	9	1	4	2				
Maintenance of standing vegetation in spring (generally less filter capacity in spring)				1				
Vegetated strips of differing ages	1							
Annual flower strips			5					

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Trait by category	Biodiversity		Biocontrol	Filter/buffer function	Biomass provision	Aesthetics	Pests	Weeds
	conservation	Pollination						
Habitat structure								
Vegetation structure	3							
High vegetation	4			1				
Short vegetation height	1							
Vegetation cover	1							
Presence of nesting sites (bare soil)		3						
Hiding places for overwintering (for remigration into the field)			7				5	
Position/configuration								
Connectivity of the vegetated strip with other habitats	4							
Width	4		4	6				
Placement in landscape (along contour line, close to water bodies, inside the field)			1	2				
Distance between nectar/pollen resources and nesting site		1						

Note: The number in the table row indicates the number of references showing an effect on the ecosystem service. Disservices appear in italics. All references, relevant species, and further details underlying this table are presented in Appendix S1: Tables S1–S5.

literature analyzed, it appears that the buffer function is favored by a dense and stiff vegetation cover, especially with a high proportion of grasses (for sources, see summarizing Appendix S1: Table S4). The height of the buffer strip vegetation is important for the prevention of spray drift (van de Zande et al., 2010).

Our review allows us to identify five characteristics relevant for the multifunctionality of vegetated strips (Figure 2): (1) age, (2) flower cover, (3) size and width of the strip, (4) type of neighboring habitat, and (5) management. We will address these characteristics in the following sections, while design and management of vegetated strips will be discussed under question 3.

We found several studies reporting “age” of vegetated strips as favorable for biodiversity conservation: nine studies stating an optimal range between 2 and >11 years; three studies with a range between 3 and >6 years (Appendix S1: Table S1), while other studies did not identify a clear age. For example, the results of Krimmer et al. (2019) suggest that pollinators only visit and pollinate the adjacent crop from older flower fields where pollinator populations have had time to reproduce. A perennial vegetated strip with a high plant species and functional diversity may also have a taller vegetation and a more heterogeneous structure than annual vegetated strips enhancing both habitat provision and buffer function.

A high flower cover is beneficial for pollinators and natural enemies, often studied and achieved by sowing annual flower strips (see Appendix S1: Tables S2 and S3). Yet, under the right cutting regime with biomass removal, perennial strips can also produce a high and/or long-term flower abundance. Korpela et al. (2013) observed flower abundance to be three times higher in artificially sown wildflower strips compared with field margins with spontaneous vegetation (60% compared with 20%) in the first year, promoting pollination services due to the increased resource availability. However, flower abundances aligned to the level of field margins in the third year, with an approximate mean flower cover of around 30% in both wildflower strips and field margins.

The size and width of vegetated strips is a critical factor for its functionality and all ecosystem services (see Appendix S1: Tables S1–S5). We found three studies addressing width for biodiversity conservation with an optimal range of >1–6 m width, one study on conservation biocontrol with an optimal width of more than 2 m, and six studies on the buffer function with a range between 0.6 and 30 m.

Predator–prey ratios were higher in large fallows (larger than 1 ha) compared with small field margins (3 m wide) (Denys & Tschardtke, 2001). Thus, conservation biocontrol and spillover of natural enemies from the

FIGURE 2 Five characteristics summarizing the traits found for each ecosystem service researched in this review. Each characteristic has different effects on the provision of multiple ecosystem services. All characteristics are important elements to foster multifunctionality of ecosystem services in vegetated strips.

strip to the field appear to be more efficient from strips of a larger size and width. However, with regard to pollination of the adjacent field, newly sown, larger flower strips can cause a concentration of pollinators, resulting in low flower visits of the adjacent crop (Krimmer et al., 2019). The size of the vegetated strip was positively correlated with the diversity and abundance of epigeous arthropods, birds, and small game (Wagner, 2014), and for the European Hamster, it was shown that a vegetated strip must have a minimum size of 0.6 ha (Fischer & Wagner, 2016). Narrow vegetated strips can be responsible for increased mortality of birds and nest predation (Morris & Gilroy, 2008; Haddaway et al., 2018).

The width of mandatory buffer strips (1–20 m) for water protection is regulated by pesticide authorization, water protection laws, and fertilizer regulations (BMEL, 2020b; BVL & JKI, 2017). Because of pesticide and fertilizer input, the habitat quality of the strip itself is often negatively affected. In buffer strips to prevent the discharge of nutrients into surface water, a few nutrient-demanding plant species will dominate, reducing the provision of other biodiversity-based ecosystem services (Stoate et al., 2009). To avoid such effects, Stoate

et al. (2009) recommend buffer zones of more than 20 m to insure that buffer strips have a value for biodiversity. However, most field margins are less than 3 m wide (in the German Federal States, Rhineland-Palatinate 85% and in Brandenburg 45%) (Hahn et al., 2014). Thus, many field margins are currently too narrow to take full advantage of their potential provision of ecosystem services.

Vegetated strips, as part of the agricultural landscape, are strongly influenced by neighboring habitats and their connectivity. In simple homogeneous agricultural landscapes, the conservation of biodiversity by means of vegetated strips is particularly important (Herbertsson et al., 2018; Kallioniemi et al., 2017). A heterogeneous landscape improves conditions for nature conservation (Fahrig et al., 2011; Molina et al., 2014), for example, promoting pollinators (Baden-Böhm et al., 2022; Rands & Whitney, 2011) or natural pest control (Rusch et al., 2016) and vegetated strips are a useful addition to existing seminatural habitats by facilitating connectivity between habitats (Batáry et al., 2021).

Complex landscapes with a high proportion of non-crop habitats, including vegetated strips, are expected to have a

lower density of pest populations than simple landscapes dominated by farmland, as improved regulation of pests by natural enemies is possible (Bianchi et al., 2006; Thies et al., 2003). In a meta-analysis, Chaplin-Kramer et al. (2011) found a strong positive relationship between landscape complexity and the presence of generalist natural enemies on a larger spatial scale, whereas effects on specialist natural enemies occur on a smaller scale. Furthermore, large size generalist natural enemies, such as lady beetles, tend to respond to the complexity of the landscape at larger spatial scales than small specialists. In heterogeneous landscapes, insects are more likely to benefit from hedges and other structures and less from flower strips (Dietzel et al., 2019).

A guidance for landscape development can be the identification of resource bottlenecks and disruptions in key beneficial organisms over time to bring missing resources like various types of food, shelter, nesting sites and materials, or overwintering sites into the landscape (Schellhorn et al., 2015). However, creating habitats for rare, highly specialized species in intensively farmed landscapes is unlikely to be successful due to a lack of source populations from natural habitats (Kleijn et al., 2006). For conservation biocontrol, it is discussed that flower strips are particularly important for landscapes dominated by agriculture in order to mitigate the negative effects of landscape simplification (Dainese et al., 2017; Tschumi et al., 2015).

The described characteristics of multifunctional vegetated strips are interrelated and depend on each other. Supporting synergies between the characteristics will enhance the overall performance and multifunctionality of vegetated strips. Cole et al. (2015), for example, found a correlation between size and width of the strip and abundance of flowers, which increased the availability of forage for insect pollinators. In addition, we expect synergies between width and structural heterogeneity. This is a result of species and functional diversity providing more ecological niches as well as of proper management and favorable abiotic conditions. Hence, promoting pollination and conservation biocontrol, providing habitat, and conserving biodiversity can be achieved with the same measure: perennial strips with the appropriate size/width and management.

How can vegetated strips be designed and managed in order to deliver multiple ecosystem services?

In order to mitigate the negative effects of landscape simplification and to target landscape development, consideration should be given to the placement and size

of vegetated strips, the selection of a seed mix or self-establishing vegetation, as well as the mowing and maintenance practices of the strip and farming activities on the adjacent fields.

Diversity promotes biodiversity

The design and management of vegetated strips and adjacent fields strongly impacts the provision of habitat for different species, hence on biodiversity conservation. A strip composition with many different flowering plant species, as well as a diverse architecture of plant heights, promotes a diverse fauna and flora. This can be insured by sowing regionally adapted seed mixtures and combining different kinds of vegetated strips and seminatural habitats, such as flowering strips, grassy margins, or hedges. On the other hand, for rare or endemic segetal flora or annual plant species, sown vegetated strips bear the risk of displacing the existing populations (Langgemach et al., 2019). In this case, Fuchs and Stein-Bachinger (2008) recommend preserving these habitats to protect highly specialized plant species rather than creating artificial vegetated strips. When installing new strips, location away from roads and other disturbances, as well as sufficient width and overall size, are also beneficial for maintaining biodiversity (see Appendix S1: Table S1).

The timing and frequency of mowing can influence the quality and function of vegetated strips. Mowing dates of vegetated strips often follow farm workflow efficiency, or they are regulated by AES (MLUK, 2020; MUKLV, 2022). In contrast to the practical management issues, most beneficial arthropods, including pollinators, profit most from unmanaged, perennial flower strips (Boetzl et al., 2021). An exception are large carabids, which profit from two cuts per year (Rouabah et al., 2015). Annual cuts and the removal of biomass are beneficial for plant diversity and the reduction of competitive plant species (Natural England, 2013; Tarmi et al., 2011), while uncut grass and flower strips become less biodiverse over time (Vickery et al., 2009).

There are greater differences in birds and mammals for different types of vegetated strips and management (see Appendix S1: Table S1). Small mammals such as common shrew benefit from cuts at larger intervals, for example, every 2 or 3 years (Aschwanden et al., 2007; Askew et al., 2007).

Birds can have very differing demands on their habitats, foraging, and nesting sites. They can benefit from uncut flowering strips, but also from different timing of cutting, which generates a diversity of swards (Vickery et al., 2009; Wagner, 2014). For example, Douglas et al. (2009) recommend frequent cuts to create patches of short,

open vegetation to promote foraging for invertebrates by birds such as yellowhammers (*Emberiza citrinella*). Short swards are generally associated with lower abundance and diversity of invertebrates (McCracken & Tallowin, 2004; Vickery et al., 2001). Short, sparse swards have been shown to enhance foraging efficiency for bird species such as passerines by increasing prey accessibility and detectability (Butler & Gillings, 2004; Stillman & Simmons, 2006; Wilson et al., 2005) and reduce the risk of being preyed upon (Whittingham & Evans, 2004). They also improve productivity and local population trends for skylark (*Alauda arvensis*) (Donald & Morris, 2005; Morris et al., 2004) and northern wheatear (*Oenanthe oenanthe*) (Arlt et al., 2008; Pärt, 2001). Many ground-nesting bird species prefer a short vegetation for their nesting period between April and July (Fuchs & Stein-Bachinger, 2008). However, management with short vegetation may discriminate many arthropod-related ecosystem services, as they require nectar and pollen from vegetated strips in late summer or need tall vegetation as overwintering sites (Douglas et al., 2009).

The timing of mowing also matters, as it promotes or suppresses species or negatively affects their development. For example, it is recommended to cut field margins once in May to reduce grass dominance, but this may conflict with the breeding season for birds and hares or migration of juvenile amphibians (Fuchs & Stein-Bachinger, 2008). Also, for butterfly conservation, any mowing during the summer months threatens butterfly populations, depending on the species (Feber et al., 1996). Fuchs and Stein-Bachinger (2008) summarized trade-offs in species

protection with regard to different management measures and types of vegetated strips (Table 2).

The information compiled in Table 2 can guide the decision for specific management options and types for different groups of organisms. In general, to promote biodiversity, staggered mowing in time or space insures that different vegetation heights and blooms are present.

Beauty is in the eye of the beholder

There is a discrepancy between the ecological values of the species in a flower strip and the aesthetic and economic demands of seed mixtures. To improve public perception and image, annual flower strips with large and colorful flowers such as sunflowers and common mal-lows are sown next to roads and tourist trails. However, as public awareness for biodiversity conservation is rising, farmers, tourists, and environmentalists alike may appreciate also small-flowered seed mixtures, unkempt field margins, and off-road locations.

Avoiding fertilizer and pesticide drift on field margin strips promotes habitat benefits

Nitrogen fertilization has been shown to have a great impact on the functional composition of plants, favoring more nutrient-demanding species (Fried et al., 2018), on butterfly species composition (Hahn et al., 2015), and on

TABLE 2 Evaluation of different management measures and types of vegetated strips with respect to their habitat-providing quality for different species groups.

Management and type of vegetated strip	Farmland birds	Hedge birds	European hare	Amphibians	Butterflies	Wild bees	Locusts	Weeds and wild flora
Late first cut (1 or 2 weeks later than usual) ^a	+							
Late or no second cut ^a	++		++	-				
High cut	+		+	++				
Bird strip	++	+			+	+		
Butterfly strip					++	+	+	
Amphibian strip		+		++	+	+		
Flower strips	++ ^a				+	+		
Field margins on fertile/rich soils		+			++	+	+	
Field margins on poor and dry soils		+			++	+	++	-
Riparian buffer strips		+		++			+	-

Note: Adapted and expanded from Fuchs and Stein-Bachinger (2008, p. 132); Wild bees were added by the authors of this review. Signs: +, a positive effect; ++, a strong positive effect; -, a negative effect.

^aFor some species only.

species richness of the field boundary (Kleijn & Verbeek, 2000). The removal of plant material from the vegetated strip helps to reduce the nutrient load and creates better conditions for wild flora and birds (Bedard-Haughn et al., 2004). Fried et al. (2018) found the joint factor of in-field practices (fertilization and herbicides), field size, and the frequency of field margin management to favor small nitrophilous species with early flowering and rapid acquisition of resource capacity. Vegetated strips must not be treated directly with pesticides, but pesticide spray drift can affect them. Insecticidal spray drift has a direct effect on butterflies, but can also affect them sublethally (Longley & Sotherton, 1997), for example, when acting as a repellent (Hahn et al., 2015). In a monitoring study, Hahn et al. (2015) found that the mean abundance of caterpillars in the field margin was 35%–60% lower than in meadows. Freier et al. (2002) tested the influence of spray drift of a pyrethroid insecticide on a field margin: Effects of the insecticide on sensitive mites were observed while other sensitive species like the lady beetles remained unaffected. However, it has been shown that locusts in particular are sensitive to extermination by insecticides and do not recolonize the sprayed areas (Triltsch et al., 2001). Bakker et al. (2021), on the other hand, could not find consistent negative effects of insecticide use in adjacent fields on the egg predation and parasitism of cabbage moth (*Mamestra brassicae*) within field margins. They concluded that field margins could act as valuable habitats supporting natural enemies irrespective of the insecticide use intensity at the local and landscape scale.

Management decisions in the field, for example insecticide use, also strongly affect the retrieval of a service such as conservation biological control. For example, generalist predators like pirate bug (*Orius* species) need the presence of non-crop habitat for refuge or overwintering, while their populations multiply in extensively managed arable fields that provide pollen and prey (Veres et al., 2012).

Herbicides also affect exposed plant species—besides mortality—through reduced biomass or suppressed flowering (Gove et al., 2007; Schmitz et al., 2013) and thus indirectly impact plant-dependent herbivore and pollinator species. For example, butterflies depend on plants in both life stages as butterflies and larvae. The effects on nontarget species vary depending on the type of target plants of the herbicides. Therefore, the choice of herbicide has a direct effect on the abundance of specific weed species (Dover et al., 1990). For herbicides, due to their mode of action, the indirect effects outweigh the direct toxic effect, which would require higher concentration of the active substances than exposure by spray drift or runoff (Brust, 1990; Michalková & Pekár, 2009; Millot et al., 2015).

The partly reversible decline of populations of species present in vegetated strips is caused mainly by the loss of

habitat due to indirect effects of herbicide treatments (Prosser et al., 2016). This entails varying degrees of negative impacts, such as removing food resources or shelter for butterflies, vegetation structures for web spiders, and the removal of plants resulting in a different microclimate and (different) shelter for beetles (Prosser et al., 2016). Similar effects were observed by other researchers who compared field margins exposed to spray drift for the abundances of polyphagous predators, spiders, aphid-specific predators, total predatory arthropods, spring tails, and aphids (Chiverton & Sotherton, 1991; Moreby, 1997; Moreby & Southway, 1999). The intensity of herbicide use (in general) has been shown to result in a slight decrease in species richness, but not in functional composition or diversity (Fried et al., 2018).

Managing for pollination and pest control

An approach to promote particular key arthropods for pollination and conservation biocontrol is the creation of customized flower strips for ecosystem services. However, the efficiency of ecosystem services varies between years, depending on the neighboring crop species, the pressure of pest populations, or environmental conditions affecting both pests and beneficial arthropods.

Krimmer et al. (2019) suggest sowing flowering strips in the first year next to cereal fields to promote conservation biocontrol and plan for older strips adjacent to pollination-dependent crops like oilseed rape and sunflowers although the older strips have fewer flowers but an established pollinator population that spills over into the crop in a search for flowers.

Buffer function is difficult to combine with habitat provision and biodiversity conservation in the strip

Buffer strips provide a filter and distance function to prevent nontarget areas from fertilizer and pesticide input via drift, runoff, and erosion. They are positioned along contour lines, water courses, forest edges, or other habitats. Concerning runoff and erosion, a high proportion of grasses is recommended for an improvement of the filter function (Dosskey, 2001; Van Dijk et al., 1996). Tall vegetation increases the screen effect of spray drift in nontarget areas and therefore increases the buffer strip efficiency (Hackett & Lawrence, 2014). However, pesticide and fertilizer input negatively affects the habitat quality of the strip itself (Stoate et al., 2009). In order to provide optimal multifunctionality, vegetated strips must be wide enough to insure a central area unaffected by pesticide drift and

fertilizers as habitats for both, sensitive species and species adapted to the agricultural landscape. Stoate et al. (2009) recommend buffer zones of more than 20 m to avoid negative effects on the strip itself and insure a value for biodiversity. Besides sufficient width of the strip, BVL and JKI (2017) recommend the use of 90% drift reducing technology and edge nozzles if no other distance regulations apply.

Biomass provision, economic aspects, and farmers' acceptance

The use of biomass from vegetated strips is underrepresented in the reviewed literature. One reason may be that the use of flower strip biomass for biogas or silage is neither allowed in AES in Germany nor under the Cross Compliance regulations (Nitsch et al., 2017). Studies have shown that flower strip biomass is not as economic as, for example, maize for biogas production (Biertümpfel et al., 2015; Degenbeck, 2020). However, positive ecological effects of flower strips in combination with maize cropping should not be underestimated (von Redwitz et al., 2019). Mixtures for biogas can be optimized for a high biomass harvest, possibly including fertilization and late harvesting (Kronenbitter & Oppermann, 2012).

Only a few of the studies we reviewed included the effects of ecosystem services on crop yields, and the conclusions varied. In a meta-analysis with 11 studies, Albrecht et al. (2020) could not find any effect of flower strips on the yield of the adjacent field, neither by the number of plant species richness in the flower strip nor by the time since establishment or landscape simplification. Other studies found a yield increase in winter wheat in close proximity to the vegetated strip (Tschumi, Albrecht, Bärtschi, et al., 2016), whereas yield decreased in winter wheat close to different AES (Boetzel et al., 2020). In oilseed rape, yield increased indirectly proven by insect pollination (Woodcock et al., 2016) and also in tomato depending on the type of vegetated strip but independent of pest damage (Balzan et al., 2016). Vegetated strips occupy land that could be otherwise used for crop production, but Pywell et al. (2015) found equivalent yield increases in insect-pollinated field bean when low-yielding margins were enhanced for pollinators and other beneficial insects. This is complemented by the fact that higher weed pressure and higher soil compaction reduce yields at the crop edge anyways (Raatz et al., 2019; Wilcox et al., 2000).

Multifunctional landscapes conserving natural capital for stocks and flows of ecosystem services do not necessarily reduce yields (Kremen & Miles, 2012; Pretty, 2008). Still, yield data and a calculation of the economic balance are important to convince farmers to implement flower

strips (Haddaway et al., 2018; Uyttenbroeck et al., 2016). Costs also include regular mulching or the ecologically more valuable removal of the biomass (Noordijk et al., 2011). In Switzerland, farmers' acceptance of field margins was related to crop yields and to the costs relative to the value of the crop (Jacot et al., 2007). The opportunity to adjust the width of the unsprayed edges was also considered important, as well as the motivation to improve the conditions for biodiversity (Jacot et al., 2007).

Avoiding disservices

Disservices and farmers' acceptance are crucial considerations for the successful introduction of vegetated strips. Unwanted effects occur if, for example, annual weeds colonize the field (De Cauwer et al., 2008). Thus, recommendations focus on plant community composition. For example, promoting perennial species, specific grass species, or grass-flower mixes significantly reduces the prevalence of hog weed (*Heracleum sphondylium*), nettles (*Urtica dioica*), brome grass (*Bromus sterilis*), and thistles (*Cirsium arvense*) (Marshall & Moonen, 2002). In addition, weed-specific adaptations in management regimes of vegetated strips may help to prevent and/or reduce weed occurrence, for example, removing the biomass after mowing may reduce noxious vegetative propagated weeds (De Cauwer et al., 2008). For the reduction of couchgrass (*Elymus repens*), more than one cut per year is necessary (Tarmi et al., 2011). Many vegetated strips are regularly mown in order to prevent natural succession but also to reduce the likelihood that vegetation will harbor harmful species, for example, weeds, slugs, or mice that threaten the crop. Appendix S1: Table S5 provides an overview of traits of vegetated strips that promote pests and weeds.

DISCUSSION

Benefits of vegetated strips and policy-related measures to foster their implementation

The need and value of the conservation and promotion of biodiversity are well acknowledged in science and politics and demanded by society. In the previous sections, we discussed the benefits for biodiversity, landscape connectivity and aesthetics, pollination and biological control as well as their function as buffer zones and in biomass production. We summarize that perennial strips are preferable to annual strips for a

number of reasons but require adapted management such as staggered mowing to insure their value for biodiversity, providing refuge and overwintering places and food for a large number of species. Furthermore, sufficient width of vegetated strips safeguards undisturbed areas, a broad diversity of food resources, and, ideally, can connect structures at the landscape level. Nevertheless, the simultaneous provision of the services habitat and biodiversity conservation as well as buffer is not always feasible. Local conservation needs such as buffering and filtering functions to protect watercourses may be paramount, but could also include elements of structural or species diversity.

Recent national legislation like the special framework action plan “Measures for insect protection in agricultural landscapes” (BMU, 2019) and the related funding schemes will support to some extent the conducive measures to enhance functional biodiversity. For example, the federal state of Saxony (SMUL, 2021) incentivizes perennial flowering strips, including specific seed mixtures, or perennial self-vegetating fallow strips at field edges, which persist for at least 5 years. In particular, overwintering structures must remain. The strip width can range between 6 and 20 m. Additionally, the redesign of the CAP with the proposed eco-schemes is a chance to improve the measures to foster multifunctional vegetated strips.

When designing targeted subsidies for multifunctional vegetated strips, the farmers’ perspectives and management options should be considered and linked to the traits that are conducive to the provision of ecosystem services by vegetated strips. In reality, trade-offs will occur on spatial and temporal scales as well as between the perspectives of biodiversity and management practices. The acceptance and willingness of farmers to establish or enhance vegetated strips depend on the administrative procedures involved and the costs of the management. In a German study, the three reasons most often cited by farmers for not implementing vegetated strips were high bureaucratic burden, low subsidies, and anticipated problems with landowners (Mante & Gerowitt, 2009). In another study (DBV, 2016), German farmers were asked about the reasons why a majority (71%) did not report vegetated strips as ecological focus areas under the EU-Greening scheme. The main reason was that they had alternatives (38%) to meet Greening requirements, for example, intercropping, undersowing, or fallowing. Those remained the preferred and most reported measures (87%) in Germany (BMEL, 2020a). Other reasons for not establishing vegetated strips included lack of operational capabilities (21%) and off-farm obstacles (27%), such as complicated requirements, excessive effort, risk of sanctions, and

insufficient information (DBV, 2016). Moreover, studies broadly lack the inclusion of economic aspects and thus miss to deliver convincing economic arguments for the introduction of vegetated strips. An important, but to-date lacking, prerequisite is the economic assessment of all costs and benefits to conclude on the compensation of farmers’ losses by implementing vegetated strips (e.g., for seed, tillage, and land taken out of production) compared with growing a crop. Furthermore, an economic analysis of annual vegetated strips (lower seed costs, annual sowing) compared with perennial vegetated strips (higher seed costs, single sowing) is required to positively support the decision-making for the implementation of vegetated strips and to safeguard their contribution to the various ecosystem services. Managing multifunctional vegetated strips can be challenging, and the need for advisory services results in higher costs.

Reliability of data, research gaps, and limitations of this study

In our review, we observe an imbalance in the literature addressing the functionality of ecosystem services provided by vegetated strips. For example, the buffer capacity, due to its higher predictability based on physical factors, and the necessary width of the vegetated strip are well studied and allow statements to which level the adjacent habitats are protected from agrochemicals.

Similarly, habitat and resources for biodiversity and aesthetics are well studied, yet the experimental proof and data availability of other ecosystem services and especially multifunctionality are still sparse. In our search, we found no studies on traits and measures influencing soil micro- and macro-organisms and their role in the filtration of runoff from the adjacent field, except for earthworms on a species level.

Many studies estimating pest control effects focus on traits that favor the presence of natural enemies in vegetated strips without measuring the actual extent of pest control in the field, or focus on pest abundance without considering the effectiveness of conservation biocontrol (Veres et al., 2013). A reliable estimation of pest control is difficult, because pest control (in the field) is measured by the abundance of pests at a given (crop sensitive) time and not over time (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011).

All reviewed studies face the limits of data collection and use guilds or other subsets of species as proxy for the functioning of ecosystem services. Thus, for several traits and measures, we could only find effects on a species that is involved in the provision of a certain ecosystem service.

There is a general limitation that many studies do not list the plant species sown in the vegetated strip. In a review on biodiversity effects of flower strips by Dietzel et al. (2019), less than 50% of the studies reported the sown plant species. Therefore, the distinction between sown strips and naturally generated strips and their effects were also beyond the scope of this review. Further problems arise in variances of the experimental setup of studies and thus methods and interpretation of effects (Dietzel et al., 2019).

Climate and climate change are additional factors with many uncertainties and pose challenges for management and prediction of ecosystem service provision. Annual weather fluctuations affect both natural enemies (Vandereycken et al., 2013) and pests (Hatt et al., 2017). Weather variations can also determine whether fluctuations in populations of natural enemies coincide with pest outbreaks or pollinators coincide with the flowering season. Effects of climate change on plant phenology have already been observed (Menzel et al., 2020). By increasing biodiversity, vegetated strips are expected to stabilize ecosystem services and thus the agro-ecosystem under climate change.

While existing data can be used to estimate the multifunctionality of the ecosystem services, only few studies have addressed multiple ecosystem services directly in the field (Denys & Tschardtke, 2001; Douglas et al., 2009; Van Rijn et al., 2019; Woodcock et al., 2016). Thus, the multifunctionality of ecosystem services potentially provided by vegetated strips has not been described experimentally. Summarizing the traits for ecosystem service provision by vegetated strips only allows us to hypothesize how the traits are connected and how they may contribute to multifunctionality, but not to consider the dynamics within those traits or the ecological dynamics within organisms.

CONCLUSIONS

By reviewing the existing literature, we identified multiple ecosystem services provided by vegetated strips, characteristics of vegetated strips necessary for the provision of specific services, and we were able to identify levers in vegetated strips that can positively affect the provision of multiple ecosystem services. Our review gives indications for the design of multifunctional vegetated strips. They can provide both ecosystem services to the field but also to biodiversity conservation. However, there are some trade-offs either between target species or ecosystem services.

To balance these trade-offs, a targeted combination of vegetated strip traits can be implemented in an

agricultural landscape to address different species, respecting the conservation needs of the species in question and thus contributing to multifunctionality.

We deduced the following recommendations for the implementation of multifunctional vegetated strips in Germany:

1. Perennial flower strips tend to have larger effects for diversity than annual flower strips, fostering a more stable provision of ecosystem services.
2. Vegetated strips should have a minimum width of 3 m in order to compensate for effects on arthropods due to pesticide drift.
3. Narrow vegetated strips need to be enlarged to provide sufficient refuge for biodiversity.
4. In narrow strips, spray drift must be prevented by using appropriate drift reduction technologies.
5. Connectivity of vegetated strips with other habitats must be insured so that source populations can avoid disturbance from management activities, colonize new habitats, and allow gene exchange between populations.

There is a lack of studies that assess the economic aspects of managing the various vegetated strips and the subsequent costs, as well as the benefits of ecosystem services. Data on these costs and benefits can inform the design of subsidies to improve their cost–benefit ratio.

Future studies need to investigate multiple ecosystem services simultaneously to estimate synergies and trade-offs with greater accuracy.

We conclude that there are promising traits that enable the creation of multifunctional vegetated strips. To outweigh trade-offs, a variety of differently managed strips should be promoted at the landscape level to complement multifunctional vegetated strips to insure the functionality and viability of all ecosystem services.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed to the conceptualization of the manuscript. Lukas Schütz conducted the literature search, filtered the references for relevance, and wrote the manuscript. All authors read, revised, and contributed in the revision of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

No data were collected for this study.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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